

Bone Loss, Its Patterns & Rationale of Bone Grafting

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The final and most severe effect of the inflammatory process seen in periodontitis is bone loss. In periodontitis, the inflammatory reaction to the bacterial biofilm insult damages the periodontal unit and causes bone loss as well as the breakdown of periodontal ligament fibres. As a result of previous pathologic episodes, the bone loss takes place but soft tissue changes may or may not correspond to it. Therefore, the depth of periodontal pockets, the severity of pocket wall ulceration, or the presence or absence of suppuration do not always correspond with the degree of bone loss.

The ultimate indicator of bone health is bone loss rate.

When periodontal disease was allowed to worsen untreated, **Löe & colleagues** discovered that the average rate of bone loss for facial surfaces and roughly 0.3 mm per year for proximal areas.

Never the less, depending on the condition that is present, the pace of bone loss may change. On the basis of inter proximal loss of attachment and tooth mortality (loss of attachment can be equated with loss of bone, although attachment loss predates bone loss by around 6 to 8 months), **Löe and colleagues¹** also found the following three subgroups of individuals with periodontal disease:

1. Approximately 8% of persons had a rapid progression of periodontal disease that was characterized by a yearly loss of attachment of 0.1 mm to 1 mm.
2. Approximately 81% of individuals had moderately progressive periodontal disease with a yearly loss of attachment of 0.05 mm to 0.5 mm.
3. The remaining 11% of persons had minimal or no progression of destructive disease with a yearly loss of attachment of 0.05 mm to 0.09 mm.

Factors affecting the morphology of osseous defects:

The form of the osseous defect depends on the location of causative microorganisms on the root surface, form of dental arches and vascular pathways, root and root trunk anatomy, thickness of alveolar bone root position within alveolar process and the proximity with adjacent involved root surface. In wide arches, craters and intrabony defects predominate, and in the narrow arches, the margin is destroyed leading to the formation of inconsistent margins which may be associated with an interproximal crater or a hemiseptum. At the base, which is wider than the crest, the infrabony defect may develop only at the apical third of the root.²

There are two general theories about the determinants of site and morphology of bone defects:²

- 1) Form of the defect is related to occlusal stress on the related teeth or tooth (**Glickman and Smulow 1962**)⁴
- 2) Form of the defect is related to the original anatomy of alveolar process (**Prichard 1965**)⁵

The potential relationship of occlusal trauma to the severity and/or progression of periodontal disease have been documented in the past literature with no clear conclusion. Polson and Zande⁶ concluded that trauma superimposed upon existing intrabony pockets increased loss of alveolar bone and altered osseous morphology, but did not affect the loss of connective tissue attachment. Also no association has been documented between increase in probing depth in the presence of occlusal discrepancies.⁷ The role of occlusal trauma in the etiology of periodontal disease has been strongly associated with other factors such as oral hygiene and smoking. Traumatic occlusion may play only a secondary function in the initiation and progression of periodontitis.⁸⁻¹¹

Goldman & Cohen (1958)¹² have included traumatic lesions of the attachment apparatus among the other possible factors in the pathogenesis of the bone defects like tooth anatomy and position, the relationship of adjacent marginal ridges and cemento enamel junctions and open contact points with resultant food impaction.

The Different Classification Systems Describing The Various Types Of Defect

Having a thorough knowledge about the morphology would help the clinicians in ideal decision making regarding the techniques and materials used for regeneration. For example, a defect with more bony walls would present with more osteogenic surface area, and lead to a predictable regeneration with or without bone grafts.

Osseous defects in periodontitis have been broadly classified into Horizontal bone loss and Angular bone loss. Horizontal bone loss is the most common pattern of bone loss in periodontal disease. The bone is reduced in height, but the bone margin remains approximately perpendicular to the tooth surface. Such a shallow linear defect between marginal bone of the radical cortical plate or interdental crest, extending the length of one or more root surfaces, usually formed by socket side resorption and deposition of facial surface known as marginal gutter.

Vertical or angular defects are those that occur in an oblique direction, the base of the defect is located apical to surrounding bone.¹³

Suprabony defects are those where the base of the pocket is located coronal to alveolar crest. Infrabony defects are defined by the apical location of the base of the pocket with respect to the residual alveolar crest. Another term that has been used in the literature is the intrabony lesion. The terms Infrabony and intrabony have been used interchangeably in the periodontal literature. In a recent guest editorial by **Mea A. Weinberg & Robert N. Eskow**, have designated the term Infra bony periodontal defects as all angular or vertical periodontal defects and intrabony defects as specific type of 3- wall condition with specific morphology and a higher potential for regeneration than other types of bony defects.¹⁴

The definitions in the classification systems are not based on the radiographic assessments but on the actual morphology of the defects after flap elevation.²

Goldman &Cohen (1958)¹²:

It is one of the most commonly used systems till today. They classified the vertical defects on the basis of the number of remaining walls.

**Glickman (1964)¹⁵:
Described bone deformities as:**

- Osseous craters
- Infrabony defects
- Bulbous bone contours
- Hemisepta
- Inconsistent margins
- Ledges

Osseous craters: These are concavities in the crest of the interdental bone confined within the facial and lingual walls.

Infrabony defects: These are hollowed out troughs in the bone alongside one or more denuded root surfaces, enclosed with one, two, three or four bony walls.

Bulbous bone contours: Bony enlargements caused by exostoses, adaption to function, or buttressing bone formation.

Hemisepta: The remaining portion of an interdental septum, after the mesial or distal portion has been destroyed by periodontal disease.

Inconsistent margins: These are angular or U - shaped defects produced by resorption of the facial or lingual alveolar plate, or abrupt differences between the height of the facial or lingual margins and the height of the interdental septa.

Ledges: These are plateau-like bone margins caused by resorption of thickened bony plates

Prichard's Classification (1966)¹⁶

He included in his classification furcal invasion and combinations of one, two and three walled pockets. Defects in interalveolar bone were classified as:

- Interproximal craters
- Inconsistent margins
- Hemisepta
- Furcation Involvement
- Intrabony defects (infrabony defects with three osseous walls)
- Combination of these defects

Crater was defined as a wide mouthed cup or bowl shaped defect in the inter alveolar bone, with bone destruction about equal on the roots of the contiguous teeth; the side walls of the crater are formed by marginal bone on the vestibular and lingual surfaces.

The intrabony defect is a specific osseous defect with definite morphology; it is not just any defect with the base of a periodontal pocket apical to the alveolar crest.

Karn et al (1983)¹⁷

He gave a topographic classification of deformities of the alveolar process as:

- Crater
- Trench
- Moat
- Ramp
- Plane/ Horizontal bone loss
- Cratered ramp
- Ramp into a crater or trench

Crater: A crater is formed as a result of loss of alveolar bone and a portion of the contiguous supporting alveolar bone from only one surface of a tooth.

Faciolingual cross section of crater

Facial view of crater

Trench: Is when bone loss affects two or three confluent surfaces of the same tooth. Trenches can be similarly identified by the tooth surfaces involved (e.g., mesiofacial, mesio-lingual-distal, etc.).

Trench

Moat: When the previously described deformity involves all four surfaces of a tooth, it is described as a moat.

Ramp: In its purest form the term ramp describes a deformity that results when both alveolar bone and its supporting bone are lost to the same degree in such a manner that the margins of the deformity are at different levels.

Ramp (facial view)

Mesiofacial ramp in a cross section of crater

Plane: This term is applied when both alveolar bone and supporting bone is lost to the same degree such that the margins of the deformity are at the same level. It can be considered horizontal bone loss about one tooth or portion of a tooth.

Cratered ramp: It is basically a crater with a portion of its facial and/or lingual wall missing. Cratered ramps are named for the teeth involved, the aspect of the alveolar process from which bone has been lost in the ramp portion and the tooth interproximally, may also be seen facial and lingual to the teeth.

Cratered ramp

Mesial ramp into crater

Ramp into a crater or trench: The most coronal aspect of the deformity is distinctly a ramp and the apical portion is distinctly a crater or trench.

Furcation invasions: Descriptions of furcation invasions should include a notation of the degree of involvement (Class I, II or III).

Fenestration is a circumscribed defect in the cortical plate which exposes the lingual or facial root surface.

In fenestration and dehiscence a connective tissue covering overlies the osseous lesion and is firmly attached to the root surfaces by periosteal fibers^{18,19}. During the surgery a fenestration can become dehiscence due to removal of the necrosed remaining thin layer of marginal bone.²¹ Thus these defects are regarded as therapeutically tricky.

Circumferential defects classification:

In 1966, Wade evaluated the flap operations for correcting the osseous defects his report stated that repair may depend on circumferential aspect of the infra bony defect and the selection of the cases was recommended with particular regard for circumferential topography.²⁰ So a classification system was developed in an effort to expedite the portrayal of the horizontal surface aspect of most periodontal deformities by Jules

Klinsberg (1979)²¹

Klinsberg²² proposed a classification with four aspects namely periodontal pockets, gingival recession, osseous pockets and osseous recession. He divided them mostly into four classes depending upon the number of surfaces and corners involved by the periodontal disease.

Papapanou PN et al 2000²

He has enlisted all the commonly used and most popular classification system for each category. For the osseous defects he included the supra bony and infrabony (according to **Goldmen and Cohen**)¹² and the furcation involvement classification by **Hamp et al** (horizontal component)²³ and **Tarnow & Feltcher**²⁴ (Vertical component) as a first level of classification for the periodontal defects.

Furcation Defects Classification:

Most of the classifications related to the furcation areas depend upon the extent of bone loss in the radicular area of the furcation. The modifications later on introduced included the vertical component of bone loss along with horizontal component.

Glickman classification (1953)²⁵

Glickman was one of the first to classify furcation invasions based on the degree of lateral penetration of the periodontal destruction under the roof of the furcation. He divided them into the following four grades:

Score	Criteria
<i>Grade-I</i>	I. Incipient ii. Pocket is suprabony and primarily affects soft tissue. iii. Early bone loss with increase in pocket depth.
<i>Grade-II</i>	i. Can affect one or more furca of tooth. ii. Cul-de-sac with definite horizontal components. iii. Multiple defects do not communicate as a portion of alveolar bone remains attached to the tooth. iv. Extent of horizontal probing decides early or advanced lesion. v. Radiograph may or may not depict. iv. Presence of furcation arrow indicates possible furcation involvement.
<i>Grade-III</i>	i. Bone is not attached to furcation dome.. ii. Opening may be filled with soft tissue in early stage. iii. Probe may not completely pass through furcation because of interference with bifurcation ridge or facial / lingual bony margins. iv. Buccal and lingual probing dimensions equals furcation dimensions.
<i>Grade-IV</i>	i. Interdental bone destroyed. ii. Soft tissue receded apically to furcation opening, visible clinically. iii. Funnel exists between the furcation and probe passes readily

Goldman et al classification (1958)²⁵

- Grade I Incipient.
- Grade II Cul-de-sac.
- Grade III Through-and-through.

Hamp et al (1975)²³

Hamp et al modified the Lindhe and Nyman classification by adding the component of prognosis for the treatment modalities.

- **Degree I**
 - o Horizontal loss of periodontal tissue support not exceeding one third of the width of the tooth.
- **Degree II**
 - o Horizontal loss of periodontal support exceeding one third of the width of the tooth, but not encompassing the total width of the furcation area.
- **Degree III**
 - o Horizontal through-and-through destruction of the periodontal tissue in the furcation.

Tal and Lemmer (1982)²⁷

Vertical component of the classification was added to predictably determine the prognosis for various treatment modalities. The degree of severity of the furcation defects affecting each molar is assigned to one of four groups designated 1, 2, 3 and 4, referred to as furcation involvement index (FII) scores.

- Furcal rating 1. Depth of the furcation is 0 mm.
- Furcal rating 2. Depth of the furcation is 1 to 2 mm.
- Furcal rating 3. Depth of the furcation is 3 mm.
- Furcal rating 4. Depth of the furcation is 4 mm or more.

Tarnow & Fletcher (1984)²⁴

Each grade of furcation is further subdivided into three subgroups, based on the degree of vertical involvement.

- Subclass A 0–3 mm
- Subclass B 4–6 mm
- Subclass C >7 mm

Fedi (1985)²⁸

Combined Glickman and Hamp classifications: Grades are same as Glickman's grades I through IV, but grade II is subdivided into degrees I and II.

Degree I

The furcation bone loss possesses a vertical component of >1 but 3 mm, but still does not communicate through-and-through.

Walter et al. (2009)²⁹

They modified the Hamp et al classification by adding a specific digital number to delineate different classes

Degree II is divided into:

- **Degree II.**
 - o Horizontal loss of support >3 mm, but no more than 6 mm.
- **Degree II–III:**
 - o Horizontal loss of support >6 mm, but no detectable "through-and-through" destruction.

Classification of Peri Implant Defects:

It is necessary to classify the peri implant defects and have a thorough knowledge of the configuration of these defects so as to help the clinician to decide whether to carry out a resective or regenerative therapy as may be applicable for defect filling.

Spiekermann Classification (1984):³⁰

Classified the peri implant defects on the basis of the clinical status of the peri implant bone and the required therapy.

- Class I- Horizontal
- Class II- Key-shaped
- Class III a- Funnel-defect
- Class III b- Gap-like defects
- Class IV- Horizontal-circular

Spiekermann classification (1995):³¹

- **Class I**
 - o Slight horizontal bone loss with minimal periimplant defect
- **Class II**
 - o Moderate horizontal bone loss with isolated vertical defects
- **Class III**
 - o Moderate to advanced horizontal bone loss with broad circular bony defects
- **Class IV**
 - o Advanced horizontal bone loss with broad circumferential vertical defect as well as loss of oral and/ or vestibular bony wall.

Type I

Type II

Type III

Type IV

Vanden et al (2004):³²

- **Type 1 defect:** Closed defect
 - o The surrounding walls are maintained
- **Type 2 defect:** Open Defect
 - o Which lack one or more bone walls

Schwarz et al 2008:³³

- **Class I defects**
 - o Intraosseous defects
- **Class II defects**
- o **Supra-alveolar defects**

Prevalence:

Periodontal Defects:

Bony defects prevalence has been reported to be 18% (Nielsen)³⁴, 32% (Wouters and Salonen 1988)³⁵, 60.8% (Persson 1998)³⁶, 45% (Soder et al)³⁷, 51% (Ainamo et al 1998)⁴².

Osseous craters have been documented as the most common intrabony defects and comprised 62% of all the bony defects in the mandible. (Manson and Nicholson 1974)⁴³ also reported by Saari et al⁴⁴ the highest prevalence was of craters (5.35%) followed by intrabony defects (4.10%) and hemisepta (0-5%).

Age:

Higher prevalence of bony and furcation defects has been noted in older age. (Nielsen, Papapanou et al, Wouters et al)^{38, 45, 46}

The frequency of crater defects increased with age. (Gilmore 1970, Larato 1970, Nielsen et al 1980)^{47, 48, 38}

In terms of location:

Craters have been found mostly between the 2nd and 3rd molars. Usually the heights of the lingual and buccal crest were equal in 85% of craters (Saari et al)⁴⁴, if unequal then the buccal crest were located apically than the lingual crest.

In case of hemiseptal defects the mesial surfaces of roots were more involved than distal roots⁴⁹. Same was reported by Muller et al⁵⁰ who stated the prevalence of the intrabony defects deeper on mesial than on distal which was in accordance to other studies by Persson and Wouters FR.^{40, 46}

Fenestration were more common in maxilla (37% in maxillary 1st molar, 13.9% in maxillary canine and 11.5% in mandibular canine) while dehiscence was more commonly seen in mandible (12.9% in cuspids, 11.3 % left maxillary molar)⁵¹

Furcation has also been reported to have higher prevalence in maxilla than mandible. Highest prevalence of class 2 and class 3 was observed at distal site of maxillary first molar (53%) and least in mesial aspect of maxillary second molar.⁵²

Diagnosis:

The detection and accurate assessment of the location, extent and configuration of the endosseous defect is important for determination of the tooth prognosis, the treatment plan and maintenance procedures (**Papapanou&Wennstrom 1991**)⁵³

Visual Examination:

The exact topography of the alveolar process affected by periodontal disease can be determined only by visual examination during surgery. It can be done by two methods: one by Open Bone Measurements Using Probe and another is Impression Method.

Probing:

Careful probing during clinical examination is essential and pocket depth and width can be determined, but there are limitations and probing does not verify the precise position of the bone.

Bone Sounding:

This method is a trans-gingival probing technique that is used, under anesthesia, to plot the morphological outline of the defect. Because bone sounding gives consistent measurements that are equivalent to open bone measurements, and in addition avoids a re-entry procedure, it can be considered as a good substitute for open bone measurements.

Radiographs:

The IOPAs show the vertical position but not the width of the alveolar process in the septal regions. The appropriate depth of absorption may be seen, but neither the width of septal bone nor the buccolingual position of the deformity can be recorded.

It's difficult in identifying subtle osseous changes⁵⁴⁻⁵⁷ (**Goldman, Prichard, Bender, Ramadan**), due to the presence of structured noise which consists of anatomic features that are not of specific diagnostic interest.⁵⁸

Other shortcomings are elongation of the radiographic image. The image may apparently “grow or destroy” alveolar bone independent of any real change in the alveolar bone support. Variations in the contrast and density of a radiograph, caused by poor control of film processing, or variation in KVP or exposure time, may burn out the alveolar crest independent of changes that are in the two-dimensional nature of conventional radiograph.⁵⁹

Periapical radiographs are susceptible to operator error, especially in maxillary molar region. (**Hausmann 1989**)⁶⁰. Using a radiographic grid and Schei ruler have been employed to reduce the discrepancies.⁵⁹

Comparison of the radiographic and direct measurements showed that they were equal or differed by ± 1 mm in 140 pairs (87.5%) of measurements.⁶¹

Panoramic Radiography:

Advantage of using panoramic radiographs is a large amount of information while exposing the patient to low level of ionizing radiation. (**Gonzalez 2001**).⁶² One of main limitations is the potential for image distortion (Mol A).⁶³ In patients with Chronic Periodontitis and Aggressive Periodontitis, panoramic radiographs often under or overestimate linear distances. A study by Kim ST stated that panoramic radiographs may be an alternative to the set of intraoral radiographs but cannot replace them.⁶⁴

Digital radiography & Subtraction radiography:

Subtraction radiography reduces structured noise, increases the detectability of radiographic changes and improved diagnostic accuracy.⁶⁵ This technique permits visualization of change in image densities at different time intervals and allows detection of mineral changes as little as 5%.⁶⁶

The two technical obstacles to clinical implementation of this technique include the use of unwidely custom occlusal templates and the need for computer assistance.⁶⁵

The radiation dose is reduced to 80-96% in direct digital method. When such systems are coupled with image processing computers and mass storage devices such as optical disks, the comparison of multiple radiographic examinations is facilitated.⁶⁵ CADIA (Computer-assisted densitometric image analysis) method has been applied and it presents bony changes in terms of CADIA units which are related to the gray level changes.⁶⁷

Computed Tomography:

CT has been explored as it enables cross-sectional and three dimensional analysis without distortion. But CT is impractical because of machine cost, complexity, high radiation and relatively low resolution.⁶⁸

In addition DVT (digital volume tomography) than offers better imaging quality than CT but with a slight deviation in the dimension.

More recently, Cone beam computed tomography (CBCT) was introduced for head and neck application.⁶⁹⁻⁷³ CBCT examination takes approx 30 seconds, and radiation is within range of an intraoral full-mouth series^{74,75}. The CBCT measurements are comparable to traditional methods, with advantage of allowing observance of periodontal defects in all directions.⁶⁸

These advances in radiography reduce the radiation exposure but their utility in periodontal and periimplant defect diagnosis is less due to the cost factor.⁶⁸

Fiberscopes:

Fiberscopes are based on fiberoptic endoscopy technology, and they are minimally invasive miniature periodontal endoscopes with which a magnification of 24-48X can be achieved. Fiberscopes, when applied clinically as reported by **Ozawa et al. (1999)**⁷⁶ allowed visualization of the fields involved in periodontal disease. When inserted through a fistula, the extent of bone loss, the soft tissues and root surfaces involved in periodontal lesions could be differentiated. It can also be applied to furcation diagnosis; however, to date there are no studies conducted to assess the efficacy of fiberscopes in furcation measurements.

Optical coherence tomography (OCT):

The optical coherence tomography system uses a white light that is able to penetrate into the tissues without biologically harmful effects. Differences in the reflection of the light are used to generate a signal that corresponds to the morphology and composition of the underlying tissues. It has been reported to be a

novel diagnostic device and as a sensitive method for identifying periodontal defects (Otis et al., 2000)⁷⁷. This system is implicit to be able to provide both 2- and 3-dimensional intraoral images with good lateral and axial optical resolution and good microstructural detail.⁷⁸

Ultrasonography:

It is a non-invasive investigation technique that uses a very high frequency (7.5-20 MHz) pulsed ultrasound beam to produce high-resolution images of structures. As the ultrasound waves travel through the tissues, some of them are reflected back by tissue interfaces to produce echoes that are picked up and converted into electrical signals, which in turn are converted into black, white and grey images and are displayed on a computer screen. Using ultrasound in osseous defects diagnosis, a study by **Chandra shekhar et al. (2014)**⁷⁹ showed that it was 76% accurate as compared to surgical measurements (clinical measurements showed 70% accuracy). Further studies, however, are required to substantiate its effectiveness in osseous defects measurements.

Clinical Significance:

The Regeneration Potential Score (RPS) of the defects can be calculated by the no. of osseous defect walls present for the predictability of the regeneration.

For vertical defects:

Type of Defect	Vascularized Osseous Walls		Flap Interface		Root Surface Walls		R.P.S
3 Osseous Walls	3	+	1	-	1	=	3
2 Osseous Walls	2	+	1	-	1	=	2
2 Osseous Walls	2	+	1	-	2	=	1
1 Osseous Walls	1	+	1	-	1	=	1

For Furcation defects:

Type of Defect	Vascularized Osseous Walls		Flap Interface		Root Surface Walls		R.P.S
Crestal Lesions	1	+	1	-	2	=	0
(Inter-Proximal Facial & Inguinal Dehiscence)	0	+	1	-	1	=	0
Class II Furcations	2	+	1	-	3	=	0
Class III Furcations	1	+	1	-	3	=	-1

Rationale of bone grafting:⁷⁰

The results of systematic reviews and meta-analysis show that

- 1) In comparison to open flap debridement (OFD) operations, bone grafts raise the bone level, decrease crestal bone loss, increase clinical attachment level, and minimize probing depth;
- 2) There are no differences in clinical outcome parameters between calcium phosphate (hydroxyapatite) ceramic and particulate bone allograft grafts; and
- 3) compared to graft alone, bone grafts with barrier membranes increase clinical attachment level and decrease probing depth.

Using grafts to treat Class II furcations had positive therapeutic outcomes. 3Demineralized freeze-dried bone allograft (DFDBA) supports the development of a new attachment apparatus in intrabony defects, whereas OFD causes periodontal repair that is primarily characterised by the growth of a long junctional epithelial attachment.

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